

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

SYNTHESIS OF NITROGEN-CONTAINING COOLIGOMER AND STUDY OF ITS INHIBITORY PROPERTIES

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Abstract

At the time of rapid development of technology in all fields of industry worldwide, corrosion protection of equipment and facilities made of metal, mainly in oil refining enterprises, is one of the urgent problems. Much of this problem falls on the oil sector, as it is associated with the failure of equipment and metal structures due to atmospheric corrosion during oil and gas production, processing and transportation. These important problems caused by corrosion processes continue to grow every year, however, this problem also leads to a sharp change in the environmental factors of our planet.

Every year, 10-15% of manufactured metal parts fall into disrepair as a result of corrosion, and this struggle does not lose its relevance, but is increasing day by day. Although it is not possible to completely prevent the corrosion process, there are various ways to relatively reduce its speed, the simplest of which is the use of anti-corrosion inhibitors, which are also easy to apply.

One of the important problems is the use of modified cooligomers with nitrogen-containing organic compounds in the preparation of coating compositions and inhibitors in the corrosion protection of equipment and facilities used in the oil and gas production industry, as well as in oil refining enterprises. The use of anti-corrosion inhibitors in these industries has shown high through their expedient use. The use of corrosion inhibitors in industries has not only resulted in its effectiveness, but is also due to the fact that it has universal indicators and is cost-effective [1-2].

Modification of existing phenol-formaldehyde, epoxide and resorcin-formaldehyde oligomers with nitrogen-containing organic compounds with positive results leads to a decrease in the amount of free monomers in the composition by about 5-7 times, a multiple increase in temperature indicators with an increase in the mass of the molecule led to an increase in stickiness, toughness and degree of solidification, and performance indicators with an increase in functionality [3-4].

The novelty of the research work is that the resorcinol-formaldehyde oligomer modified by copolycondensation method and obtained with a new composition, ecologically clean and economically favorable inhibitor is studied in reservoir water taken from "SHIRVAN OIL OPERATING COMPANY", sea water and ordinary water and the investigation of its areas of use.

Keywords: modification, cooligomer, corrosion, reservoir water, inhibitor

In the research study, resorcinol-formaldehyde oligomer was modified with amide group compound and its inhibitory properties were studied for the first time. Modification of resorcinol-formaldehyde oligomer was carried out by sopolycondensation method in acidic environment. The main indicators of the so-oligomer obtained were studied. For the purpose of comparison, the resorcinol-formaldehyde oligomer was also synthesized in the laboratory under the same conditions and its main indicators were studied. It was found that the amount of free formaldehyde in the sooligomer decreased by about 2-3%, the softening temperature increased from 80°C to 95°C, and the

density increased from 1150 kg/cm³ to 1225 kg/m³. The IR spectrum of both the modified oligomer and the unmodified resorcinol-formaldehyde oligomer was studied for comparison. From the comparative analysis of the spectra, it became clear that the process is a chemical modification, and the presence of an amide group in the newly obtained compound gave reason to use it as an inhibitor. In the second stage of the conducted scientific-research work, a formation water sample taken from "Shirvan Oil Operating Company" was used. The ionic composition and physical-chemical indicators of formation water were taken from the laboratory of the specified organization (Table 1)

Table 1

Ionic composition of formation water, mg/l									
Horizon	Total mineralization, g/l	Viscosity, spz	Anions				Cations		
			Cl ⁻	HCO ₃ ⁻	SO ₄ ⁻	Naph-thenic acid	Na ⁺ K ⁺	Ca ⁺⁺	Mg ⁺⁺
PsAr2	14.64-19.32	0.52-0.58	8956-11857	40-123	9	48	4390-5765	1012-1407	60-179
Ps2Ar2	17.86-27.09	0.57-1.02	10976-17073	62-92	7	47-119	5443-7368	931-1632	211-1245

In order to determine the inhibitory properties of the resorcinol-formaldehyde oligomer, experiments were first carried out in laboratory conditions. For this purpose, 20x40x2 mm steel-D samples were taken. The composition of the steel-D sample consists of elements such as carbon, 14.22%, manganese 14-65%, silicon 12-13%, sulfur - 5%, phosphorus - 4%. The amount of the inhibitor was calculated according to 11 of corrosion medium. The study was conducted at room temperature (20±50°C) for 6 hours with constant stirring. After the test period, the sample was washed, dried and weighed on an analytical scale. For the purpose of comparison, the experiment is also carried out in an environment without inhibitors, and the corrosion rate (k), protection degree (z), protection effect (γ) is determined by the gravimetric method [5]:

$$\text{Corrosion rate: } K = \frac{m_0 - m_1}{st}, q/m^2 \text{ saat} \quad (1)$$

Here, m_0 is the weight of the sample before corrosion, g; m_1 -mass of the sample after corrosion, g; S-sample area, m²; t-study period;

$$\text{Protection degree: } Z = \frac{k_0 - k}{k_0}, \% \quad (2)$$

Here, k_0 – corrosion rate without inhibitor, k – corrosion rate with inhibitor

$$\text{Protection effect: } \gamma = \frac{k_0}{k} \quad (3)$$

In order to check the effectiveness of the inhibitor, laboratory studies were conducted in a comparative manner in 3 environments - reservoir water, sea water and distilled water. Formation water was taken from 2 wells of "SHIRVAN OIL OPERATING COMPANY" (PsAr2 and Ps2Ar2) and tested on steel samples of different sizes. The concentration of the inhibitor was calculated according to 200, 400, 600 mg/l. 0.2, 0.4, 0.6 mg of cooligomer was dissolved in 10 ml of solvent and mixed separately for 6 hours. 0.2, 0.4, 0.6 mg of sooligomer was dissolved in 10 ml of acetone and the weight of the steel plate was calculated after 6 hours in the solvent medium. The protective efficiency, degree of protection, and corrosion rate of different amounts of inhibitor against the corrosion of carbon steel samples in formation water were calculated and shown. (Table2)

Table 2

Effect of modified resorcinol-formaldehyde cooligomer on corrosion of steel in formation water environment

Serial №	Horizon	Corrosion rate (k) in medium without inhibitor, g/m ² hour	Inhibitor concentration, mg/l	Modified resorcinol-formaldehyde cooligomer		
				K, g/m ² hour	Z, %	γ
1	PsAr2	0,457	200	0,0014	99,7	387,8
			400	0,0011	99,8	493,6
			600	0,0007	99,9	775,7
2	Ps2Ar2	0,543	200	0,0021	99,5	217,6
			400	0,0018	99,6	253,8
			600	0,0004	99,9	114,2

The role of hydrogen in the corrosion process in aqueous, alkaline and acidic environments is important, and H₂S is considered the most dangerous factor. It causes corrosion of gas equipment, metal structures, tanks and pipelines. The next stage of the research was continued in sea water. The effect of the inhibitor on the corrosion of steel in seawater - the corrosion rate, the protection effect and the degree of protection - have been studied and shown in Table 3.

Table 3

Effect of modified resorcinol-formaldehyde cooligomer on corrosion of steel in seawater						
Serial №	Horizan	Corrosion rate (k) in medium without inhibitor, g/m ² hour	Inhibitor concentration, mg/l	Modified resorcinol-formaldehyde cooligomer		
				K, g/m ² hour	Z, %	γ
1	PsAr2	0,543	200	0,0018	99,6	287,3
			400	0,0010	99,8	537,6
			600	0,0001	99,9	285,8
2	Ps2Ar2	0,457	200	0,0019	99,5	236,7
			400	0,0011	99,6	387,2
			600	0,0002	99,9	157,8

Corrosion of modified resorcinol-formaldehyde oligomer in distilled water environment was tested in both wells and shown in Table 4.

Table 4

Effect of modified resorcinol-formaldehyde cooligomer on corrosion of steel in distilled water environment						
Serial №	Horizan	Corrosion rate (k) in medium without inhibitor, g/m ² hour	Inhibitor concentration, mg/l	Modified resorcinol-formaldehyde cooligomer		
				K, g/m ² hour	Z, %	γ
1	PsAr2	0,543	200	0,0030	99,4	181
			400	0,0017	99,6	135,7
			600	0,0004	99,9	319,4
2	Ps2Ar2	0,457	200	0,0030	99,3	148,0
			400	0,0011	99,7	415,4
			600	0,0003	99,9	152,3

It is clear from the conducted studies that many factors affect the corrosion process of equipment and facilities made of steel. These are influenced by the chemical composition, the concentration of the inhibitor, the nature of the corrosion environment, general mineralization and other factors. Thus, resorcinol-formaldehyde cooligomer modified with an organic compound containing amide group can be used as an inhibitor against corrosion of steel in the indicated environment[6].

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